

THE INFLUENCE OF PRICE, PERCEIVED QUALITY, SERVICE QUALITY TOWARD PURCHASE INTENTION OF DOMESTIC MOTORCYCLE IN VIETNAM

Nguyen Phan Duc Hoa¹, Filda Rahmiati^{2*}, Intan Syaffinatun Nida³

Management, President University, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author

Filda Rahmiati

Management, President University, Indonesia.

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Abstract: Motorcycle becomes main transportation in Vietnam which create huge demand. In fact, the existences of International Business create competition for domestic motorcycle product in the market. Thus, the purpose of this research is to determine the influence of Price, Perceived Quality and Service Quality toward Purchase Intention to domestic motorcycle in Vietnam. This research focuses on Ho Chi Minh area considering as the biggest city in Vietnam and has the most motorcycle as well as the highest percent population own motorcycle. The researcher distributed questionnaires using the quantitative method and collected 109 respondents as samples. The researcher only focuses on the people who buy a domestic. With data processing using SPSS 22, the results revealed that the specific Price, Perceived Quality and Service Quality have a significant influence toward Purchase intention to buy domestic motorcycle. Adjusted R-Square result of three variables on consumer Purchase Intention towards domestic motorcycle in Vietnam in this study was 61.6% while the remaining 38.4% were affected by other factors not included in the research model being studied. Overall, the research had achieved the objectives of the research as well as brings recommendations to Vietnamese motorcycle manufacture and future researcher.

Keywords: Domestic Motorcycle, Price, Perceived Quality, Service Quality, Purchase Intention.

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Introduction

Vietnam is a developing country with a population of 97.8 million people, ranked 14th worldwide as per November 2019 (PwC Vietnam & VCCI, 2019). The motorbike market, Vietnam is the 4th largest in the world, just after the countries with the largest population in the world such as India, China and Indonesia (Motorcycledata.com, 2019).

The number of motorcycles currently circulating is about 58,170,000 units compared to 1,209,000 units in 1990. In average 60,03% Vietnamese population own a motorcycle. Motorcycle still suitable with the transportation infrastructure in Vietnam and it more convenient compare with car (Lim, 2018). Added, The Ministry of Transport, motorcycles will still be the main means of transportation of Vietnamese people. According to experts' forecast, the motorcycle market is still a potential market in Vietnam, in the period of 2018-2021 the number of motorcycles will increase by 1.12 million units and by 2030 will increase by 1.62 million units (Đúc, 2019).

Based on Motorcycledata.com, (2019), shows the average new motorcycles had been sold in 2018 in Vietnam is much higher

than other countries. Especially in Ho Chi Minh City is known as the city with the most motorcycles in Vietnam, and the percentage of motorcycles owners is also the top in the country. With the current population of 8.99 million people as per September 2019 (Thi, et al., 2019), according to Ho Chi Minh City Department 16,204 11,213 24,483 35,894 9,853 0 5,000 10,000 15,000 20,000 25,000 30,000 35,000 40,000 India China Indonesia Vietam Pakistan Average new motorcycle sold per 1,000,000 people in 2018 (unit) 3 of Transport, in June 2019, Ho Chi Minh City has 8.12 million motorcycles and 825,343 cars (Ha, 2019). If calculating the total number of cars and motorcycles, on average, each person in Ho Chi Minh City owns a motorcycle or a car.

According to the latest reports from The Vietnam Association of Motorcycle Manufacturers (VAMM), the number of motorcycles produced and sold in the country has highest in year 2018 (Figure 1.3). Hence, in the first quarter of 2019, motorcycles in the market down by 6.1 percent (Vamm.org.vn, 2019). Further, as Honda is the most trusted brand accounting for 75.9% of the market but in the first three quarters, the number of motorcycles sold did not meet the manufacturers expectations. Data from The Vietnam Association of Motorcycle Manufacturers (VAMM) in 2019 averaging losing 4.4% compared to the same period last year.

Detail in 2019, in Q1 down 6.2%, in Q2 down 5.3%, in Q3 down 4.4% and in October down 6.1% (Vamm.org.vn, 2019).

Some factors that influence the purchase intention, which is direct related to sale and profit (Walone, 2016) especially motorcycles such as brand, price, perceived quality, services, customer satisfaction (Mehmood & Shafiq, 2015). To find out the factors that influencing purchasing intention toward domestic motorcycle, the researcher has to research what factor influence consumer intention toward buying domestic motorcycle. Even though various of factor, the researcher just focusses on price, product quality and services have affected the purchasing intention of Vietnamese people living in Ho Chi Minh City toward domestic motorcycle.

Since Asean Free Trade Area (AFTA) regulations which was valid in 31 December 2015, all trade with ASEAN country will have 0% tax fee, created opportunities for imported motorcycles to compete directly with domestically produced ones. According to the General Department of Customs, the volume of imported motorcycles consumed in May 2019 increased by 31.9% compared to the same period last year (Nguyen, 2019). It has a certain influence on domestic motorcycle manufacturers. So that in this case, the researcher is going to find out that how price, product quality and services have influence purchase intention in buying domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

Literature Review

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is a crucial aspect of consumer behavior, influencing transactions between buyers and sellers (Raza, et al., 2014). It involves activities like searching, selecting, buying, using, and evaluating products and services to meet needs (Walone, 2016). Understanding consumer intention helps businesses make informed decisions about price, product, and service quality (Benedick, 2017). Purchase intentions are also vital in marketing, as they influence consumer choices and forecast future sales (Anjum & Abbas, 2019). Marketers use purchase intentions to plan actions to attract consumers and predict future sales (Morwitz, 2014). However, purchase intentions and actual purchases are closely related, assessing future consumption effectiveness (Hiep, 2017).

Price

Price is the value customers sacrifice for benefits of a product or service (Kotler, P., et al., 2018). It is a sensitive business factor that directly impacts sales and profits (Walone, 2016). Prices may vary, and are considered reasonable when in line with the product and consumer's financial potential (Lee, 2016). Indicators for price include benefits alignment, perceived value, affordability, price competition, and quality compliance (Fauzi, 2017).

Perceived Quality

Perceived quality is a crucial factor in determining the success of a product, encompassing reliability, durability, performance, aesthetics, special features, and serviceability (Napitupulu, et al., 2010). Consumers often evaluate product quality before making a purchase decision, comparing it with the perceived value (Aijaz Ali Khoso, et al., 2016). Factors used in

evaluating perceived quality include aesthetics, material quality, reliability, and conformance durability (Handoko, et al., 2017).

Service Quality

Service quality is a long-term evaluation of service performance, measured by responsiveness and customization (Lahindah, et al., 2018). It directly affects customer satisfaction and is cheaper to maintain existing customers than finding new ones (Lee, 2016). Service quality is influenced by customer service, employee attitude, and warranty service (Widyastuti, et al., 2017). According to Handoko et al., (2017), service can be adjusted by serviceability, which is relating to speed, competence, ease and accuracy in providing services for the repair of goods.

Relationship between Price and Purchasing Intention

Price plays an important role in considering and deciding whether to buy or not (Chen, et al., 2017). Therefore, price is considered as a direct factor affecting purchase intention. In the purchasing process, price is the most important factor that can change consumer purchasing decisions (Rahmanullah & Nurjanah, 2018). This research will see how price influence the purchase intention toward domestic motorcycle.

Relationship between Perceive quality and Purchasing Intention

In making a purchase decision, price and perceived quality are two factors that have a direct influence on the purchase intention (Chadha, 2011). Perceived quality significant affects consumer decision to buy motorcycle (Amron, 2018).

Relationship between Service quality and Purchasing Intention

Good service quality can influence consumer pay attention toward a product (Wiyadi & Ayuningtyas, 2019). The quality of goods and service quality are the two factors that influence consumers' acquisition of products (Lahindah, et al., 2018). In the previous research (Lahindah et al., 2018); (Lee, 2016); (Morwitz, 2014); (Wiyadi & Ayuningtyas, 2019) have the same result that service quality has influence consumer purchasing intention.

Research Framework

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Source: Constructed by Researcher 2019

Methods

This research utilized primary and secondary data, with primary data consisting of first-hand information collected through questionnaires. Secondary data was gathered from previous

journals, newspapers, and reputation websites, and analyzed using SPSS 22. The study utilized a questionnaire to collect data on Price, Perceived Quality, Service Quality, and Purchase Intention, using a Likert-style rating questionnaire with a five-point scale.

This research aimed to gather data from motorcycle consumers in Vietnam, specifically in Ho Chi Minh, using a non-probability sampling with convenience sampling technique. The researcher collected 109 respondents to ensure accuracy in the data. The questionnaire was distributed via social media and distributed to others until enough data was collected. The survey was conducted online due to physical distance, and the confidence level was 95%, with a margin error of 5% or 0.05. Two programs were used to analyze the data: Microsoft Excel 2016 for tabulating the data and SPSS version 22.0 for analyzing classical assumption tests, hypothesis testing, T-tests, and F-tests. The margin error was set at 5% or 0.05. The study aimed to understand the preferences and preferences of motorcycle consumers in Vietnam.

Descriptive statistics are essential for describing data features, such as scale variables and measures. Two tools used in this research are the mean and standard deviation. The mean is the sum of values divided by the number of values, while standard deviation is the squared root of the variance.

Multiple linear regression is a statistical method that uses the least squares method to estimate the relationship between a dependent variable Y and multiple independent variables Xi, determining the value of a criterion.

Testing the Hypothesis

T-Test

The T test is a statistical method used to determine the significant relationship between independent and dependent variables, by testing the null hypothesis of no multiple relationships (Cohen, L., 2011).

The level of significance that used in this research is $\alpha = 0.05$. Ho is accepted if the significant value is greater than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ and Ho is rejected if the significant value is less than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$

1. H01: $\beta_1 = 0$ or if level of significant $\alpha > 0.05$, H0 is accepted and H α is rejected

There is no significant influence of Price toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

H α 1: $\beta_1 \neq 0$ or if significant $\alpha < 0.05$, H0 is rejected and H α is accepted.

There is a significant influence of Price toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

2. H02: $\beta_2 = 0$ or if level of significant $\alpha > 0.05$, H0 is accepted and H α is rejected 30

There is no significant influence of Perceived Quality toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

H α 2: $\beta_1 \neq 0$ or if significant $\alpha < 0.05$, H0 is rejected and H α is accepted

There is a significant influence of Perceived Quality toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

3. H03: $\beta_3 = 0$ or if level of significant $\alpha > 0.05$, H0 is accepted and H α is rejected

There is no significant influence of Service Quality toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

H α 3: $\beta_1 \neq 0$ or if significant $\alpha < 0.05$, H0 is rejected and H α is accepted

There is a significant influence of Service Quality toward Purchase Intention of domestic motorcycle in Vietnam.

F-Test

The F-test is used to determine the relationship between independent variable components (coefficients) and the dependent variable simultaneously. The hypothesis is that the coefficient X (for example, the slope of the line) is 0. The level of significance that used in this research is $\alpha = 0.05$. Ho is accepted if the significant value is greater than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ and Ho is rejected if the significant value is less than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$.

H0: $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = 0$, H0 is accepted and H α is rejected

H α : at least one of $\beta_i \neq 0$, H0 is rejected and H α is accepted

Adjusted R squared

The coefficient of determination (R^2) essentially measures how far the model's ability to explain endogenous variation. Adjusted R^2 has been adjusted to the degrees of 31 freedom of each of the squares included in the calculation of Adjusted R^2 . The adjusted R-squared gives the best estimate of the degree of relationship in the basic population (Karch, 2008).

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1. Respondents Data

Demographic Information	Category	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	60
	Female	40
Age	<20 years old	44
	20-29 years old	33
	30-39 years old	15
	>40 years old	8
Occupation	Employee	42
	Student	20
	House wife	13
	Other	25
Monthly Income	< 7,000,000 VNĐ	13
	7,000,001-12,000,000 VNĐ	33
	12,000,001-17,000,000 VNĐ	30
	> 17,000,001 VNĐ	24

Source: Conducted by researchers

The research found that the majority of respondents were male, with 60% being male and 40% being female. The majority of respondents were aged between 20 and 29, with 44% being

between 20 and 29 years old. The majority of respondents were employed, with 42% being employees. The majority of respondents had incomes between 7,000,001 to 12,000,000 VNĐ per month, with the rate of 1 USD = 23,100 VNĐ in December 2019. The majority of respondents were housewives and had incomes between 12,000,001 to 17,000,000 VNĐ per month.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistic result

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation
X1	109	1	5	3.47	.786
X2	109	2	5	3.37	.740
X3	109	1	5	3.54	.719
Y	109	2	5	3.50	.700
Valid N (listwise)	109				

Source: Conducted by researchers

The table 2. above shows the respondents' response to statement about the Price (X1) as "P", Perceived Quality (X2) as "PQ", Service Quality (X3) as "SQ" and Purchase Intention (Y) as "PI". The most dominant variable in term of independent is Service Quality with the minimum value of 1 and maximum value of 5 and mean value of 3.54.

Pre-Test Result

Result of Validity Testing

Researcher had already conducted the pilot test with 30 respondents in order to test the validity and reliability. In testing validity of the questionnaire, researcher used Pearson product-moment coefficient of correlation with help of SPSS windows version 22. Based on the output of the SPSS, with significant level of 5 per cent and r-table of 0.361 (see R-value for n=30), all the statements in the questionnaire are valid since the r computation is bigger than r table. The details are shown in the tables below:

Table 3. Price – Validity result

Variable	Question	R-table (a=5%)	R computation value	Description
Price	P1	0.361	0.723	Valid
	P2	0.361	0.705	Valid
	P3	0.361	0.692	Valid
	P4	0.361	0.527	Valid
	P5	0.361	0.547	Valid

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Table 4. Perceived Quality – Validity result

Variable	Question	R-table (a=5%)	R computation value	Description
Perceived Quality	PQ1	0.361	0.281	Invalid
	PQ2	0.361	0.780	Valid
	PQ3	0.361	0.739	Valid
	PQ4	0.361	0.661	Valid
	PQ5	0.361	0.661	Valid

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Table 5. Service Quality – Validity result

Variable	Question	R-table (a=5%)	R computation value	Description
Service Quality	SQ1	0.361	0.719	Valid
	SQ2	0.361	0.802	Valid
	SQ3	0.361	0.771	Valid
	SQ4	0.361	0.518	Valid

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Table 6. Purchase Intention – Validity result

Variable	Question	R-table (a=5%)	R computation value	Description
Purchase Intention	PI1	0.361	0.610	Valid
	PI2	0.361	0.687	Valid
	PI3	0.361	0.764	Valid
	PI4	0.361	0.616	Valid
	PI5	0.361	0.645	Valid

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Since there was one statement not valid (PQ1), it will be removed from further analysis in this research and all of the valid statements had been used.

Result of Reliability Testing

Reliability testing used to measure the reliability of the instrument to use in collecting the data. Researcher used Cronbach's Alpha to test the reliability of the data with help of SPSS windows version 22.

Table 7. Reliability Result

Variable	N of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Price (X1)	6	.743
Perceived Quality (X2)	5	.812
Service Quality (X3)	5	.794
Purchase Intention (Y)	6	.791

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Classical Assumption

This research is going to use multiple regression in analyzing data, so firstly it has to do classic assumption testing, where in this case, researcher is using three kinds of assumption as follows:

Normality Test

For this test, a good regression model has the normality distribution among independent variables and dependent variable. In doing normality test, there are two ways used in this research: Histogram and Normal P-Plot Regression Standardized Residual.

Figure 1. Histogram

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Based on the histogram above, the curve shows that the data has spread to all normal curve area and the curve skews in the center of the histogram. By looking at this histogram, the researcher can conclude that the data has a normal distribution. The researcher also used P-P plot as consideration to analyze the normality of data. The reason is that histogram less effective and less certain especially when the data is small. Therefore, this plot will estimate the empirical data and approximate particular theoretical distribution.

The figure below shows the points stay around the line, and it means that there is a normality distribution. This normality distribution allows the research goes further.

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Figure 2. Normal P-Plot Regression Standardized Residual

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

As shown in Figure 2. above the Normal P-P Plot of Regression seen the spread of points around the diagonal line and

follow the direction of the diagonal line. Thus, the data are normally distributed, and the data in regression model fulfils assumption normality.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is a crucial assumption in multiple regression to determine the independence of independent variables. It is used to identify highly correlated variables in models. The test is analyzed using tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). A tolerance value of over 10% and a VIF value of less than 10 are required for non-multicollinearity.

Table 8. Multicollinearity

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	VIF	Tolerance
1 (Constant)		
X1	2.369	.422
X2	2.035	.491
X3	2.263	.442

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

In this research, all variable indicators are free from multicollinearity, as indicated by $VIF < 10$ and $tolerance > 0.1$.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test is used to analyze disturbance errors caused by the same variances in one observation to another. In this research, a scatter plot was used to analyze the disturbance error. The results showed no disturbance from the same variants in one observation to another, with all plots spreading randomly. The scatter plot did not indicate any organization, indicating that the heteroscedasticity problem did not occur in this study.

Figure 3. Scatterplot

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Multiple Regression Analysis

The result from multiple linear regression test is shown on table 4.8 below. Based on the result, it will show how much the independent variables influence the dependent variable of this research.

Table 9. Multiple Regression Test Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.636	.221		2.876	.005
X1	.274	.082	.308	3.357	.001
X2	.211	.076	.235	2.766	.007
X3	.338	.087	.348	3.879	.000

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

Based on Table 9, the result of multiple regression analysis will be interpreted in the standardized form of the equation as follows:

$$Y = 0.636 + 0.274X1 + 0.211X2 + 0.338X3$$

Where,

Y = Purchase Intention

X1 = Price

X2 = Perceived Quality

X3 = Service Quality

The multiple regression analysis test results indicate that a one-point increase in price, a one-point increase in perceived quality, and a one-point decrease in service quality can increase purchase intention by 27.4% and 21.1%, respectively. Conversely, a one-point decrease in perceived quality and a one-point increase in service quality can decrease purchase intention by 21.1% and 33.8%, respectively. These findings suggest that price, perceived quality, and service quality play crucial roles in influencing consumer behavior and purchasing decisions. Therefore, adjusting these variables can significantly impact consumer behavior and purchase intentions.

Hypothesis Testing

This research is going to use multiple regression in analyzing data, so firstly it has to do classic assumption testing, where in this case, researcher is using three kinds of assumption as follows:

T-Test Significance

According to Table 9. above, the researcher indicates that three independent variables are significant. Here is the final hypothesis result:

Price (X1)

H01: There is no significant influence of Price towards Purchase Intention

Ha1: There is a significant influence of Price towards Purchase Intention the significant value of Price is .001 which is lower than α (0.05).

Therefore, the variable does have significant influence on Purchase Intention. Meaning, H01 is rejected and Ha1 is accepted.

Perceived Quality (X2)

H02: There is no significant influence of Perceived Quality towards Purchase Intention

Ha2: There is a significant influence of Perceived Quality towards Purchase Intention The significant value of Perceived Quality is .007 which is lower than α (0.05).

Therefore, the variable has significant influence on Purchase Intention. Meaning, H02 is rejected and Ha2 is accepted.

Service Quality (X3)

H03: There is no significant influence of Service Quality towards Purchase Intention

Ha3: There is a significant influence of Service Quality towards Purchase Intention The significant value of Service Quality is .000 which is lower than α (0.05).

Therefore, the variable has significant influence on Purchase Intention. Meaning, H03 is rejected and Ha3 is accepted.

F-Test Significance

Table 10. ANOVA Table, F-Test Significance Result

ANOVAa						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33.116	3	11.039	58.734	.000b
	Residual	19.734	105	.188		
	Total	52.850	108			

a. Dependent Variable: PI

b. Predictors: (Constant), SQ, PQ, P

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

H04: There is no significant influence of Price, Perceived Quality and Service Quality towards Purchase Intention

Ha4: There is a significant influence of Price, Perceived Quality and Service Quality towards Purchase Intention

Based on the table 10 above, the result of F-test is shown accurately. All of the independent variables used in this research are simultaneously significant towards Purchase Intention. It is described by the level of significance that clocks in at 0.000 which is lower than the α (0.05), with F value calculated at 58.734. Thus, H04 is rejected and Ha4 is accepted.

Adjusted R Square Table

Table 11. Coefficient Determination (R²) Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.792a	.627	.616	.43352

a. Predictors: (Constant), SQ, PQ, P

b. Dependent Variable: PI

Source: Data Processing Result of SPSS 22

The research used the Adjusted R-Square to measure the model's ability to explain variation in the dependent variable. The results showed that 61.6% of Purchase Intention is influenced by Brand Image, Perceived Price, Perceived Quality, and Perceived Value, while 38.4% is explained by other factors not associated with this study, such as Brand Image, Word of Mouth, Customer Trust, and Personality Trait.

Discussions and Interpretation of Result

The study investigates the impact of price, perceived quality, and service quality on purchase intention among domestic motorcycle customers in Vietnam. The research involved 109 respondents with a margin of error of 5% and a significance level of 95%. The results showed that 61.6% of purchase intention was explained by price, perceived quality, and service quality, while 38.4% was explained by other factors. The F-test resulted in a significant value of 0.000, indicating a significant simultaneous influence of price, perceived quality, and service quality on purchase intention. The study's findings suggest that price, perceived quality, and service quality have a significant simultaneous influence on purchase intention.

Influence of Price on Purchase Intention

The study reveals that price significantly influences the purchase intention of domestic motorcycles in Vietnam, with a T-Test result of 3.357 and a significant value of 0.001, indicating a positive brand image. Multiple linear regression results show a positive B coefficient of 0.274, indicating that price can increase purchase intention by 27.4%, confirming the hypothesis of price's significant influence.

In the same line with the previous researches by Amron (2018) and Pandowo et al., (2014), which stated that Price has a strong positive correlation Purchase Intention significantly. According to Lee (2016), price is the first priority for general customer. 49 Since price can directly affect the purchase decision (Rahmanullah & Nurjanah, 2018), price is an advantage for domestic motorcycles because it does not have to incur the costs incurred in importing as well as cheaper domestic labor, the government's preferential policies will help Vietnam domestic motorcycles to have a competitive price.

Influence of Perceived Quality on Purchase Intention

The study reveals that perceived quality significantly influences the purchase intention of domestic motorcycles in Vietnam. The T-Test result of 2.766, with a significant value of 0.007, supports the hypothesis of Ha2 (Ha2). Multiple linear regression results show a positive B coefficient of 0.211, indicating that perceived quality is a positive factor that can increase purchase intention by 21.1%.

This result is linked with the result from previous researches by Amron (2018), Lee (2016), Wiyadi & Ayuningtyas (2019), which said perceived quality influence to purchase intention, becomes one of factor determine whether consumers will buy a product. Many years ago, imported goods always had the advantage of quality with Vietnamese goods especially motorcycle. But now that consumer mind is gone, because Vietnamese motorcycles can be exported to Europe, Japan and other countries. Quality is no longer a weakness for Vietnamese motorcycles.

Influence of Service Quality on Purchase Intention

The study reveals that Service Quality significantly influences the purchase intention of domestic motorcycles in Vietnam. The T-Test result is 3.879, with a significance value of 0.000, indicating a positive influence. The multiple linear regression 50 results show a positive B coefficient of 0.338, indicating that perceived quality is a positive factor that can increase purchase intention by 33.8%.

This result is linked with the result from previous researches by Widyastuti et al., (2017), Wiyadi & Ayuningtyas (2019), which said Service Quality influence to Purchase Intention. Good Service Quality can build a positive reputation for company (Widyastuti et al., 2017) and can increase purchase Intention of consumer (Wiyadi & Ayuningtyas, 2019). Consumers not only buy motorcycles but they also want to use the services after buying them. The most complete and fastest accompanying services will attract purchase intention and help consumers gain more confidence in making purchasing decisions and in the time of using the product.

Price, Perceived Quality, Service Quality toward Purchase Intention

The study reveals that price, perceived quality, and service quality significantly influence the purchase intention of domestic motorcycles in Vietnam. The results, which are lower than the significance level of 0.05, confirm the significant influence of these factors on purchase intentions.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study examines the impact of price, perceived quality, and service quality on customer purchase intention in the case study of domestic motorcycles in Vietnam. Results show that lower prices lead to higher purchase intentions, while higher perceived quality and service quality also contribute to higher purchase intentions. The study concludes that a combination of these factors significantly influences purchase intentions.

The study recommends Vietnamese Domestic Motorcycle Manufacturers adjust prices based on technology levels, product type, and target market. They should also focus on creating new, better products with cheaper inputs. Vietnam's membership in AFTA and other international trade organizations presents both challenges and opportunities for motorcycle manufacturers. Improving service quality, such as salesmen's attitude, processing speed, and spare part availability, is crucial for improving product quality and influencing purchase intentions. Furthermore, future researchers can expand independent variable varieties, including advertising, necessity, brand image, customer trust, and consumer psychology, and expand the population to obtain objective results in other Vietnamese cities.

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